

Promotional Mix-Elements and Sales Volume: The Case of Primary Cooperatives of Coffee Farmers in West Guji Zone

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Abstract – The purpose of this study was to analyze the impact of promotional mix elements on sales volume of primary cooperatives of Coffee farmers in West Guji Zone. Quantitative research approach and explanatory type of research design was used. The data required for this study has been gained from primary sources. For the purpose of this study a pre-designed questionnaire has been distributed to a purposeful sample of 222 member of the cooperative farmers by using Simple Random sampling techniques. SPSS was used to analyze the primary data which was collected through questionnaire. A reliability Cronbach's Alpha to determine the reliability of the questionnaire as a tool to collect the necessary data was performed. Normality, linearity and multicollinearity were test. The data analysis was conducted through statistical techniques such as descriptive statistics, correlations and multiple linear regressions. The findings of this study revealed that the frequency of promotional mix elements practice in primary cooperatives of Coffee farmers in West Guji Zone was high for advertising, personal selling, and sales promotion. There was a significant positive correlation between the five independent variables (Advertising, Sales promotion, Personal selling, Public relation and Direct marketing) and dependent variable (Sales volume). There is a statistically significant effect of the following promotional mix elements: (advertising, personal selling, public relations, Direct marketing and sales promotion) carried out by cooperative members. Therefore, the cooperative members should focus on better application of Advertising, personal selling, public relations, Direct marketing and sales promotion to increase the sale volume.

Keywords: Coffee farmers, mix elements, promotional practices, primary cooperative, sales volume.

1. INTRODUCTION

The promotional mix elements refer to the various tools and strategies that organizations use to communicate with their target audience and promote their products or services [1]. These elements work together to create an integrated marketing communication campaign. It also known as the promotional mix or marketing communications mix, are a set of tools and strategies used by marketers to promote and communicate with their target audience [2]. These elements include advertising, personal selling, sales promotion, public relations, and direct marketing. Each element of the promotion mix can have an impact on sales volume, and the effectiveness of these elements depends on various factors such as the target audience, product or service being promoted, and the overall marketing strategy. Promotion mix elements are a set of tools and strategies that marketers use to communicate and promote their products or services to the target audience [3].

However, the impact of each promotion mix element on sales volume can vary depending on the product, target audience, competitive landscape, and overall marketing strategy. A well-integrated and coordinated approach that combines different elements of the promotion mix is often more effective in driving sales

volume than relying on a single element in isolation. Additionally, tracking and analyzing the results of promotional activities through metrics such as sales data, customer feedback, and market research can provide insights into the effectiveness of each element and help refine future promotional efforts [4].

Currently, there are several challenges that business experiences in the selection of appropriate promotional mix elements [5]. To select the right promotion mix elements, it's crucial to have a deep understanding of the target audience's preferences, behaviors, and communication channels [6]. However, researchers posit that there is a gap in understanding the target audience [7]. They suggested further that business lack the necessary insights into consumer behavior, competitor strategies, and industry trends. Moreover, Okoli, Aruwa [8] identified gaps in measurement and evaluation of the effectiveness of promotion mix elements. This ineffectiveness in measurement and evaluation limits the ability to assess the impact of each element accurately. Those are the reasons for that this research was initiated to be conducted in case organization to examine the relation between promotion mix elements employed and cooperative sales volume.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Framework

The relationship between the promotional mix elements and sales volume is a topic of interest in marketing and advertising [9]. The promotional mix consists of various elements or tools that organizations use to communicate with their target audience and promote their products or services. These elements include advertising, personal selling, sales promotion, public relations, and direct marketing. Theoretical perspectives suggest several possible meanings and relationships between these elements and sales volume [2]. A few theoretical viewpoints are

Hierarchy of Effects Model: According to this model, the promotional mix elements work together to guide consumers through a series of stages, including awareness, knowledge, liking, preference, conviction, and finally, purchase [2]. Each element of the promotional mix contributes to moving consumers through these stages, and ultimately, a higher sales volume is achieved.

AIDA Model: The AIDA model, which stands for Attention, Interest, Desire, and Action, suggests that the promotional mix elements are designed to capture the attention of consumers, generate interest in the product or service, create a desire for it, and ultimately lead to action or purchase [10]. By effectively utilizing the elements of the promotional mix, organizations can increase sales volume by guiding consumers through these stages [11].

Communication Effectiveness Model: This model emphasizes the role of communication effectiveness in driving sales volume. It suggests that the promotional mix elements should be designed and executed in a way that effectively communicates the value proposition of the product or service to the target audience. If the promotional messages are clear, persuasive, and resonate with the target audience, it is more likely to result in increased sales volume.

Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) Model [12]: The IMC model emphasizes the importance of coordinating and integrating all elements of the promotional mix to deliver a consistent and unified message to the target audience [13]. According to this model, when all promotional mix elements work in harmony and reinforce each other, it leads to a synergistic effect that can positively impact sales volume [14].

Sales Response Function: The sales response function theory suggests that the relationship between the promotional mix elements and sales volume is not linear but follows a specific pattern. It proposes that initially, an increase in promotional efforts leads to a significant increase in sales volume. However, as the promotional activities reach a saturation point, the incremental impact on sales volume diminishes [15]

Overall, the relationship between the promotional mix elements and sales volume is complex and multifaceted. The theoretical perspectives mentioned above provide different explanations and frameworks to understand this relationship. It is important for organizations to carefully plan and execute their promotional strategies, considering the target audience, marketing objectives, and the specific context in which they operate, to maximize the impact on sales volume [16]

While the relationship between the promotional mix elements and sales volume is generally seen as positive, there are theoretical arguments suggesting a negative relationship [17]. Over promotion Effect: This argument suggests that excessive or poorly executed promotional activities can have a negative impact on sales volume [18]. When promotional efforts become overwhelming or intrusive to consumers, it may lead to a negative reaction and resistance. Consumers may perceive the promotional messages as manipulative or deceptive, which can result in a decline in trust and ultimately reduce sales volume.

Furthermore, over promotion can lead to consumer fatigue or desensitization. If consumers are exposed to too many promotional messages, they may become immune to their effects and develop a tendency to ignore or tune out promotional efforts. This can diminish the effectiveness of the promotional mix elements and result in reduced sales volume [19].

Another aspect related to the over promotion effect is the potential dilution of brand equity [20]. When promotional activities are excessive or not aligned with the brand's identity and positioning, it can dilute the brand's perceived value and erode consumer trust [21]. This, in turn, can negatively impact sales volume as consumers may be less inclined to purchase from a brand that they perceive as overly promotional or inauthentic [22]. It's important for organizations to strike a balance in their promotional efforts, ensuring that they are targeted, relevant, and aligned with consumers' needs and preferences. By avoiding over promotion and focusing on delivering value and building strong relationships with consumers, organizations can mitigate the potential negative effects on sales volume [23].

2.2 Empirical Literature Review

Several researchers have studied relationship between promotional mix elements and sales volume and suggests significance relation. However, there is still contradicting arguments among scholars about the effects of promotional mix elements on sales volume [7, 24-26].

2.2.1 The Effect of Advertising on Sales Volume

Advertising can have a significant impact on sales volume [27]. When executed effectively, advertising can generate awareness, influence consumer behavior, and ultimately drive sales. Here are some ways in which advertising can affect sales volume [28]. Advertising plays a crucial role in creating awareness about a product or service. By showcasing the features, benefits, and unique selling propositions, advertising exposes the target audience to the existence of the product [29]. When potential customers become aware of a product through advertising, it increases the likelihood of them considering it in their purchase decisions. Advertising helps in building brand equity by establishing and reinforcing the brand's identity, values, and positioning. Consistent and compelling advertising campaigns can create a strong brand image and association in the minds of consumers. This brand equity can enhance customer loyalty, preference, and trust, leading to increased sales volume [30]. Advertising has the power to influence consumer behavior and purchase decisions. Well-crafted advertisements can evoke emotions, create desire, and persuade consumers to choose a particular product or service over competitors. By highlighting unique selling points,

demonstrating value, or presenting compelling offers, advertising can motivate consumers to make a purchase, thereby increasing sales volume. In competitive markets, advertising can help differentiate a product or service from its competitors [31]. Advertising can highlight the unique features, quality, or benefits that set a product apart. By effectively communicating these differentiators, advertising can attract customers who perceive the advertised product as superior, leading to increased sales volume. Through advertising, companies can reach a wider audience and expand their market reach. Advertising campaigns can target specific demographics, geographic regions, or consumer segments, enabling businesses to tap into new customer bases. By reaching more potential customers, advertising increases the chances of generating sales volume growth. Advertising can reinforce the purchase decisions of customers who are already considering a particular product or service. By reminding customers of the benefits, value, or reasons to choose the advertised product, advertising can strengthen their intent to purchase [32]. This reinforcement can translate into increased sales volume, especially for products with longer buying cycles or repeat purchases.

However, some researchers argue that advertising may not always have a direct impact on sales volume. They claim that advertising can create brand awareness but may not necessarily translate into immediate sales [27]. The effectiveness of advertising depends on various factors such as message clarity, targeting, and market conditions [33, 34]

Hypothesis 1: Advertising, through its ability to enhance brand awareness and perception, positively influences customer engagement and purchase intent, leading to increased sales volume.

2.2.2 The Effect of Personal Selling on Sales Volume

Personal selling can have a significant impact on sales volume [35]. According to Lestari, Sugiyanto [36] it involves direct, one-on-one communication between a salesperson and a potential customer. Personal selling allows salespeople to build relationships with customers. Through direct interactions, salespeople can establish rapport, understand customer needs and preferences, and provide personalized recommendations. Building strong relationships with customers increases their trust and confidence in the salesperson and the product, which can lead to higher sales volume. Personal selling provides an opportunity for salespeople to provide detailed information about the product or service. Salespeople can highlight the features, benefits, and value proposition of the offering, addressing any questions or concerns customers may have. By providing comprehensive product information, salespeople can help customers make informed purchase decisions, leading to increased sales volume [37]. During personal selling interactions, salespeople can address customer objections or hesitations directly. They can overcome objections by providing additional information, offering solutions, or addressing concerns [38]. By effectively handling objections, salespeople can alleviate customer doubts and increase the likelihood of closing a sale, contributing to higher sales volume. Personal selling allows salespeople to tailor solutions to meet the specific needs of individual customers [39]. By understanding customer requirements and

preferences, salespeople can recommend the most suitable product or service and offer customized options. The ability to provide personalized solutions enhances customer satisfaction and increases the chances of making a sale, thereby impacting sales volume. Personal selling provides an opportunity for salespeople to upsell or cross-sell additional products or services to customers. By understanding customer needs and preferences, salespeople can identify opportunities to recommend complementary or higher-priced offerings. Upselling and cross-selling can increase the average transaction value and contribute to higher sales volume. Personal selling allows salespeople to actively influence customer purchase decisions. Through

persuasive communication, effective sales techniques, and relationship-building, salespeople can guide customers towards making a purchase [40]. Their expertise, trustworthiness, and ability to address customer concerns can significantly impact the customer's decision to buy, leading to increased sales volume. Personal selling efforts can contribute to generating repeat business and fostering customer loyalty. By providing exceptional customer service, maintaining post-sale relationships, and offering ongoing support, salespeople can encourage customers to make repeat purchases. Repeat business is essential for sustaining sales volume over time and building a loyal customer base [41].

Critics argue that personal selling can be costly and time-consuming, making it less efficient for generating sales volume compared to other promotional mix elements [42, 43]. They claim that advancements in digital marketing and self-service options have reduced the need for extensive personal selling efforts [44]

Hypothesis 2: Personal selling, by establishing personal connections, providing tailored information, and addressing customer concerns, positively influences customer engagement and purchase intent, leading to increased sales volume.

2.2.3 The effect of Public Relation on Sales Volume

Public relations (PR) can have a significant impact on sales volume [45]. While the primary goal of PR is to manage and maintain a positive public image of a company or brand, its influence on sales can be indirect but substantial [46]. Public relations activities, such as media relations, press releases, and thought leadership articles, help build trust and credibility for a company or brand. Positive media coverage, endorsements, and industry recognition enhance the reputation and perceived reliability of a business. When customers trust and perceive a company as credible, they are more likely to choose its products or services, thus positively impacting sales volume [47]. PR plays a crucial role in shaping consumer perception of a brand. PR efforts can highlight a company's values, social responsibility initiatives, and positive impact on society. By showcasing a brand's positive attributes and aligning it with customers' values, PR can influence consumer perception and create a favorable image. This positive image can drive customer preference and contribute to increased sales volume. PR activities can generate brand recognition and increase awareness among the target audience [48]. Through media coverage, press releases, events, and sponsorships, PR helps expose a brand to a broader audience. Increased brand recognition can lead to greater consideration and preference when customers make purchasing decisions, ultimately impacting sales volume. Public relations plays a critical role in managing crises and handling negative publicity [48]. When a company faces a crisis or negative event, effective PR strategies can help mitigate the damage to the brand's reputation. By transparently addressing the issue, providing timely and accurate information, and demonstrating accountability, PR can help rebuild trust and minimize the negative impact on sales volume. Positive PR efforts can contribute to positive word-of-mouth marketing, both online and offline. When a company receives favorable media coverage, positive reviews, or endorsements from influential individuals or organizations, it can generate buzz and positive conversations among customers [49]. Word-of-mouth recommendations and testimonials have a strong influence on consumer purchase decisions, leading to increased sales volume. PR can complement and support marketing campaigns, amplifying their impact on sales volume. Integrated PR and marketing efforts can reinforce key messages, enhance campaign reach through media coverage, and create a cohesive brand narrative. PR activities can generate additional awareness and interest in marketing campaigns, resulting in increased customer engagement and sales volume.

Some opponents argue that the impact of public relations on sales volume is challenging to quantify directly [50]. They claim that while PR can contribute to brand reputation and awareness, its influence on immediate sales volume may be less direct compared to other promotional mix elements [51].

Hypothesis 3: Public relations, by managing the company's reputation, generating positive publicity, and building trust, positively influences brand perception, customer engagement, and purchase intent, leading to increased sales volume.

2.2.4 The Effect of Direct Marketing on Sales Volume

Direct marketing can have a significant impact on sales volume [52]. According to TNK, Safitri [53] it involves directly communicating with potential customers through various channels, such as email, direct mail, telemarketing, and personalized messaging. Direct marketing allows businesses to target specific audience segments with tailored messages. By using customer data and segmentation strategies, direct marketing enables companies to reach individuals who are more likely to be interested in their products or services [54]. By focusing on the right target audience, direct marketing increases the chances of generating leads and driving sales volume. Direct marketing enables businesses to personalize and customize their messages for individual customers [55]. By leveraging customer data, purchase history, and preferences, companies can create highly targeted and relevant communications. Personalized direct marketing appeals to customers on an individual level, increasing engagement and the likelihood of conversion, ultimately impacting sales volume. Direct marketing often includes a clear call-to-action (CTA) that prompts customers to take immediate action, such as making a purchase or requesting more information [56]. By providing a compelling CTA and making it easy for customers to respond, direct marketing can drive immediate conversions and sales. The direct and timely nature of the communication can result in a direct impact on sales volume. Direct marketing campaigns can be easily tracked and measured, allowing businesses to evaluate their effectiveness in driving sales volume. By utilizing unique tracking codes, URLs, or dedicated phone numbers, companies can directly attribute sales to specific direct marketing initiatives. This data-driven approach enables businesses to optimize their direct marketing efforts, refine their targeting, and maximize sales volume [57]. Direct marketing can contribute to relationship building with customers. By maintaining regular communication, providing relevant updates, and offering exclusive promotions, companies can nurture customer relationships over time. Strong customer relationships can lead to repeat purchases, word-of-mouth referrals, and increased customer loyalty, ultimately impacting sales volume positively. Direct marketing provides an opportunity for businesses to cross-sell and upsell to existing customers. By analyzing customer data and purchase history, companies can identify additional products or services that complement customers' previous purchases. Direct marketing can be used to promote these offerings, increasing the average transaction value and driving sales volume. Direct marketing plays a crucial role in customer retention and generating repeat sales [58]. By staying connected with customers through targeted communications, companies can remind them of their products or services, announce new offerings, and provide exclusive incentives. Direct marketing helps keep the brand top-of-mind, increasing the likelihood of repeat purchases and driving sales volume over time.

Critics arguments on the relationship between direct marketing promotional mix element and sales volume is that direct marketing can be intrusive and may not always resonate with customers [59]. They claim that customers are increasingly resistant to direct marketing efforts, leading to lower response rates and limited impact on sales volume [58]

Hypothesis 4: Direct marketing, through its targeted communication, personalized messages, and call-to-action prompts, positively influences customer engagement and purchase intent, leading to increased sales volume.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Approach and Design

Creswell (2014) claimed that three forms of approach to research exist, namely qualitative, quantitative and mixed approach. In this study, mixed approaches were employed. It deals with quantifying and analysis variables in order to get results. It involves the utilization and analysis of numerical data using specific statistical techniques to answer questions like who, how much, what, where, when, how many, and how (Apuke, 2017). According to Creswell (2014), quantitative research is an approach for testing objective theories by examining the relationship among variables. These variables, in turn, can be measured, typically on instruments, so that numbered data can be analysis using statistical procedures. In addition to this qualitative approach was used to analysis the qualitative data's collected through interview.

The research design is the conceptual structure within which research is conducted; it constitutes the blueprint for the collection, measurement and analysis of data. There are three types of research design, namely; exploratory, descriptive, and explanatory (Kothari, 2004). By taking the research objectives and nature of the study into consideration, descriptive and explanatory research designs were used. As stated by Kothari (2004), descriptive research studies are those studies which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual, or of a group. Hence, in this study, it used to describe the demographic and general information of the respondents and enterprise. Whereas, as suggested by (Kumar, 2016), explanatory studies clarify the relationship between two aspects of a situation or phenomena. Therefore, in this study the explanatory research design is chosen since it examine the effect of the predictors (marketing strategies) on the dependent variable (performance). The study was used mainly a cross-sectional research survey in which the collection of information from the respondents is carried out at a single point in time.

3.2 Population and Sample

The target population is the specified group of people from which sample was selected in order to develop the required data structures and information needed in the research. Since sometimes it is impossible to include the whole population in a study, it is necessary to limit the research to a section of the population (Creswell and John, 2003). The part of the population from which sample was drawn. A sample is defined as the subset of elements from the population (Kumar, 2005) selected for study purpose. It may also be defined as "any subset of the elements of the population that is obtained for the purpose of being studied" (Creswell and John, 2009). Sampling is thus the process by which elements are selected systematically from the population for the purposes of the research. The target population of this study was 500 primary cooperative farmers in the woreda.

The study adopted random sampling method to select representative sample. According to Jonson and Christensen, (2014), random sampling is frequently used in survey research, which is a non-experimental research method in which questionnaires or interviews are used to gather information and the goal is to understand the characteristics of a population based on the sample data. With randomization, a representative sample from a population provides the ability to generalize to a population (Creswell, 2009).

Accordingly, the study was used all participants selected at random. Sample size is very vital element in research methodology as it determines whether to include or excluded a participant from the study and to decide the number. Careful selection of sample size and technique makes the research finding reliable.

The sample of this research is calculated by using Taro Yamane (Yamane, 1973) formula with 95% confidence interval.

The calculation formula of Taro Yamane is presented as follow

$$N$$

Where, n=Sample size

N=Total population size e=Level of precision

$$n = 500 / 1 + 500(0.05 * 0.05) = 222$$

According to this 44 % from the total population has been used as a sample.

3.3 Data sources and Method of Data Collection

For the proper achievement of the objectives of the study; the researcher used both primary data source and secondary data source. In order to collect the data, both questionnaires and key informant interview were used. The Close-ended questionnaire was used to gather information about the thoughts, feelings, attitudes, beliefs, values, perceptions, personality, and behavioral intentions of research participants. In other words, researchers measure many different kinds of characteristics using questionnaires (Johnson and Christensen, 2014). These questionnaires are focused on getting participant responses to standardized items for the purpose of confirmatory research in which specific variables are measured and hypotheses are tested. The principle of standardization is very important in quantitative research; the goal is to provide common response categories to each person in the research study. This is done to ensure maximum comparability of responses.

In addition, closed-ended question is appropriate when the dimensions of a variable are already known. Closed-ended questions expose all participants to the same response categories and allow standardized quantitative statistical analysis (Johnson and Christensen, 2014). In this study, 5-point Likert scale questionnaire will be used. The Likert scale is an integral part of the research aim, and sometimes the purpose of the research is to understand the views and perceptions of participants with the single 'latent' variable (phenomenon of interest). Such constructed structures interact with a particular aspect of the under examination hypothesis in a mutually exclusive way and calculate the whole phenomena in unity (Kale, etal 2015). According to Johnson and (Christensen, 2014), researchers also collect data from research participants by presenting questions or statements and rating scales with instructions to use the rating scale given to make decisions on-item stem. A rating scale is a continuum of reaction options that participants are instructed to use when their responses are indicated.

3.4 Method of Data Analysis

The data that would be collected through questionnaires was analyzed and interpreted using statistical package for social science (SPSS 20 version). As result, descriptive and inferential analyses were conducted by employing different methods. In descriptive statistics mean values, frequencies and standard deviations of the respondent's answers were calculated. In inferential statistics, multiple linear regressions model and correlation analysis were used to analyze the impact and the relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

3.5 Instruments Reliability and Validity

Reliability refers to the absence of random error, enabling subsequent researchers to arrive at the same insights if they conducted the study along the same steps again; Yin, R. K., (2003). To increase the reliability of the survey, the researcher do its own efforts. The Cronbach's alpha result is greater than 0.7, revealing adequately reliability. A pilot study was conducted to refine the methodology and test instrument such as a questionnaire before administering the final phase. the respondents for pilot test will be 15 (fifteen) Questionnaires was distributed and filled before by potential respondents to make the data collecting instruments objective, relevant, suitable to the problem and reliable Issues raised by respondents were corrected and questionnaires were refined. Besides, proper detection by an advisor was also taken to ensure validity of the instruments. Finally, the improved version of the questionnaires was printed, duplicated and dispatched. The instruments selected help to show the effects of promotional Mix-Elements on sales volume

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

This chapter provides the details of data analysis and presentation of the study findings as set out in the research objective and research methodology. The promotional mix-elements on sales volume in the case of Anbesa shoe Share Company. The primary data was gathered from the questionnaire as the research instrument, the study used Likert scale and open ended questions in collecting and analyzing the data where by scale of 5 points were used in computing the means, standard deviations and inferential analysis.

4.1 Reliability Tests

Table -1: Reliability Tests

	Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Sales promotion	8	.771
Advertising	7	.781
Personal selling	3	.918
Public relation	6	.751
Direct marketing	4	.752

According to Hair, et al., (2010), If α is greater than 0.7, it means that it has high reliability and if α is smaller than 0.3, then it implies that there is low reliability. The independent variable were tested and found to be acceptable. i.e. coefficient α for each scale were found reliable where Cronbach alpha of variables were greater than 0.7, revealing satisfactory reliability as all items are developed based on theories and literature.

4.2 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

Table -2: comparisons of mean and standard deviation scores

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Sale volume	3.4645	.56214	220
Sales promotion	3.3691	.51012	220
Advertising	3.3505	.57516	220
Personal selling	3.7411	.66839	220
Public relation	3.3845	.67604	220
Direct marketing	3.3418	.67186	220
Valid N (listwise)			

Source: Computation from the Survey data (2023)

Based on the data provided in the table, the average score for the Sales Volume of Anbessa Shoe Share Company is 3.4645, with a standard deviation of 0.56214. The Advertisement mean score for the company is 3.3505, and its standard deviation is 0.57516. Similarly, the Sales Promotion mean score is 3.3691, with a standard deviation of 0.51012. The Personal Selling mean score is 3.7411, and its standard deviation is 0.66839. The mean score for Public Relations is 3.3845, with a standard deviation of 0.67604. Finally, the Direct Marketing mean score is 3.3418, and its standard deviation is 0.67186.

To categorize the extent of these mean values, we can refer to the following intervals: - If the mean value falls within the range of 1-1.49, it indicates no extent

- A mean value between 1.5-2.49 suggests a small extent
- A mean value between 2.5-3.49 indicates a moderate extent
- A mean value between 3.5-4.49 suggests a great extent
- Finally, a mean value between 4.5-5 represents a very high extent. Hence, the outcomes of the descriptive analysis lie within the realm of moderation.

4.3 Correlation Analysis of the Variables

Correlation analysis is a methodology employed to explore the connection between independent variables, assessing both their relationships with each other and their impact on the dependent variable. It aims to gauge the strength of these relationships. In this study, the correlation analysis technique is utilized to examine the robustness of the relationships between the variables under investigation. Specifically, Pearson correlation analysis is employed to furnish evidence of convergent validity.

4.3.1 Pearson Correlation Coefficients

A correlation coefficient is an effective method for summarizing the relationship between two variables using a single numerical value that ranges from -1 to +1 (Welkowitz et al., 2006). According to Morgan et al. (2004), -1 represents a perfect negative correlation, 0.0 indicates no correlation, and +1 signifies a perfect positive correlation (Kazi, 2010). From the data presented in Table 3, it is evident that there exists a significant positive correlation between the independent variables (Advertising, Public relation, and Direct marketing) except Personal selling that has insignificance relation and the dependent variable (Sales volume). The table clearly demonstrates that Advertising exhibits a strong positive correlation with sales volume. In the case of personal

selling and public relation, there is a moderate positive correlation with sales volume, while direct marketing show a strong positive correlation with sales volume.

Table -3: Summary of Correlation analysis

Constructs		Sales volume
Sales volume	Pearson Correlation	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	N	220
Advertising	Pearson Correlation	.610
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	220
Personal selling	Pearson Correlation	.107
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.113
	N	220
Public relation	Pearson Correlation	.619
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	220
Direct marketing	Pearson Correlation	.715
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	220

Source: Researcher survey analysis (2023)

4.4 Regression Analysis

Linear regression assumption diagnosis test

Test of Normality

The residuals of the model show normally distribution of the residuals. From the diagram of the histogram below it can be seen that the data is normally distributed because when we see the graph it is a bell curve shape at the center.

Fig -1: Test of Normality

Test of Multicollinearity

Multicollinearity is a problem that two or more variables giving rise to the same piece of information are included that is we may have redundant information or unnecessarily included related variables.

Table -4: Test of Multicollinearity

Independent variables	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Advertising	0.375	2.667
Sell promotion	0.312	3.207
Personal selling	0.937	1.067
Public relations	0.409	4.208
Direct marketing	0.308	5.082

Source: Survey result (2023)

The VIF results of the independent variables, as shown in the table above, are all below five. This indicates that there is no multicollinearity among them. The output provides a measure of whether there is collinearity in the data. Specifically, it calculates the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) and tolerance statistics (where tolerance is obtained by dividing 1 by the VIF). According to Andy (2010), there are some guidelines from a specific section that can be applied in such cases. If the largest VIF value is greater than 10, it raises concerns about collinearity. However, in our current model, all the VIF values are well below 10, and the tolerance statistics are well above 0.2. Hence, we can confidently conclude that there is no collinearity within our dataset.

Model summary

Regression fit a predictive model to data and uses that model to predict the values of the dependent variable from one or more independent variables. The significance level of 0.05 was used with 95% confidence interval. The dependent variable was overall sales volume and the independent variables are Promotional mix elements variables (Advertising, Sales promotion, Personal selling, Public relation and Direct marketing). We use Multiple regression analysis to examine the impacts of promotional mix elements on sales volume. The following subsections present the results of multiple regressions analysis.

Table -5: Model Summaries

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.765 ^a	.785	.776	.36623	.785	60.395	5	214	0.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Direct Marketing, Personal Sale, Advertising, Sale promotion, Public Relation

b. Dependent Variable: Sales Volume

In the above Table 4 using the linear regression coefficient of R and the corresponding R², we can assess how well the model fits the data in this study. Multiple R is the correlation between the observed value of y and the value of y predicted by the multiple regression models. Therefore large values of the multiple R represent a large correlation between the predicted and observed values of the outcome. If a variable has a small value

of R then it contributes only a small amount to the model. The above table represents the analysis of multiple regression models for the beta coefficients of each independent variable. Independent variable accounted for 78.5% of the variance in the creation of sales volume ($R^2 = 0.785$). Thus, 78.5% of the sales volume could be explained by the five independent variables (Advertising, Sales promotion, Personal selling, Public relation and Direct marketing) and other unexplored variables may explain the variation in which sales volume which accounts for about 21.5%.

Table -6: ANOVA results

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	40.501	5	8.100	60.395	.000 ^b
Residual	28.702	214	.134		
Total	69.203	219			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Direct Marketing, Personal Sale, Advertising, Sale promotion, Public Relation

b. Dependent Variable: Sales Volume

As indicated in table 6 there is statistically significant effect between independent variable (Promotional mix elements) and dependent variable (sales volume) where, (F) value was (60.395) at 0.000 which states that there is significant effect of Promotional mix elements on sales volume.

Table -7: Multiple Regression Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.406	.219		1.857	.065
Sales promotion	.329	.087	.298	3.783	.000
Advertising	.258	.070	.264	3.671	.000
Personal sales	.089	.038	.106	2.322	.021
Public relation	-.257	.111	-.309	-2.311	.022
Direct marketing	.486	.117	.580	4.158	.000

The SPSS output in the above table 7 provides details of the model parameters (the beta values) and the significance of these values. It's clear from the data in the above table that all promotional mix elements

carried out Anbesa shoe Share Company have an effect on sales volume. The first, is advertising, .258 with a value of the coefficient of the independent variable Beta, and .000 as a statistical significance, followed by sales promotion with .329 as a value of the coefficient of the independent variable Beta, and .000 as a statistical significance, followed by direct marketing with .486 as a value of the coefficient of the independent variable Beta, and .000 as a statistical significance, followed by personal sales with .089 as a value of the coefficient of the independent variable Beta, and .021 as a statistical significance and followed by public relation with -.257 as a value of the coefficient of the independent variable Beta, and .022 as a statistical significance.

4.5 Hypothesis Testing Results

The Main Hypothesis

Ho: The promotional mix elements: advertising, personal selling, sales promotion, public relations and direct marketing practiced have significant effect on sales volume.

Multiple regression analysis has been used to test this hypothesis. From the above interpretation we understand that the data in the above table that all promotional mix elements have statistically significant at the level of less than .05.

The First Sub-Hypothesis

Ho1: Advertising has significant effect on Sales volume

Multiple regression analysis has been used to test this hypothesis; the results are shown in Table 7. It's clear from the data in the above table that the value of the coefficient Beta for the independent variable advertising is .258 At 1% significance level which means we rejecting the null hypothesis

The Second Sub-Hypothesis

Ho2: Sales promotion has significant effect on Sales volume.

Multiple regression analysis has been used to test this hypothesis; the results are shown in the Table 7. It's clear from the data in the above table that the value of the coefficient Beta for the independent variable Sales promotion is .329. At 1% significance level which means we rejecting the null hypothesis.

The Third Sub-Hypothesis

Ho3: Personal selling has significant on Sales volume.

Multiple regression analysis has been used to test this hypothesis; the results are shown in the Table 7. It's clear from the data in the above table that the value of the coefficient Beta for the independent variable Personal selling is .486. At 5% significance level which means we rejecting the null hypothesis

The Fourth Sub-Hypothesis

Ho4: Public Relation has significant effect on Sales volume

Multiple regression analysis has been used to test this hypothesis; the results are shown in the Table 4.8. It's clear from the data in the above table that the value of the coefficient Beta for the independent variable public relation is -.258 at 5% significance level which means we rejecting the null hypothesis

The Fifth Sub-Hypothesis

Ho5: Direct marketing has significant effect of Sales volume.

Multiple regression analysis has been used to test this hypothesis; the results are shown in the Table 7. It's clear from the data in the above table that the value of the coefficient Beta for the independent variable direct marketing is .486 At 5% significance level which means we rejecting the null hypothesis

5. CONCLUSION

The study indicates that significant number of the employees were male than female. And the age category of the employees was in range of 20-29 which is the productive age category that can attribute for the success of the company. In cause of educational background majority of the respondents are degree holders .This implies that the employees needs further education with help of Anbessa shoe company so as to increase production and productivity of the industry.

For any business firm to be successful in their business conducting and giving attention for promotional mix element is critical part of their successful activity. Even if the company profitability is the sum of different functions such as finance marketing and other departments promotional mix elements also plays a great impact on its success through creating good public image, knowledge about the company product and increasing the amount of sales volume. Having this in to consideration this paper also tries to study and show the impact of promotional mix elements on sales volume. The study confirmed that sales promotion influenced by promotional mix elements such as Advertising, sales promotion, personal selling, public relation and direct marketing. From the mean score we understand that except persona selling all have to moderate extent usage in ASSC. Personal selling has to great extent usage in company.

The relationships between independent variables are correlated with one another and with the dependent variable. There was a significant positive correlation between the five independent variables (Advertising, Sales promotion, Personal selling, Public relation and Direct marketing) and dependent variable (Sales volume). This shows that all the factors have positive correlation and have an effect on sales volume.58.5% of the sales volume could be explained by the five independent variables (Advertising, Sales promotion, Personal selling, Public relation and Direct marketing) and other unexplored variables may explain the variation in which sales volume which accounts for about 42.5%.

There was a statistically significant effect between independent variable (Promotional mix elements) and dependent variable (sales volume) where, (F) value was (60.395) at 0.000 which states that there is significant effect of Promotional mix elements on sales volume.

In conclusion, the relationship between promotional activities and sales volume can be termed as a strong positive correlation, this is because promotional activities drive sales. If marketing department ignores the role played by promotional activities to increase the company sales volume then it neglects a very important aspect offered by the relationship. Use of promotional activities is more viable to reach and benefit the customer, they come to know about the products, their information and product availability, it makes mass distribution possible and makes customer aspire to higher and higher things in life making life a saga of continuous struggle to acquire what they do not have, as a result firms increase on their production which in turn lead to increase in sales volume.

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